

Reinforcement Learning-based User Association in Sustainable Terrestrial Non-Terrestrial 6G Networks

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Abstract—In sixth generation (6G) networks, efficient resource allocation will be pivotal to the viability of three-dimensional (3D) networks. In this paper, we study the online user association problem in an integrated Terrestrial and Non-Terrestrial (TN-NTN) 6G network, with the objective of maximizing energy efficiency subject to capacity and Quality of Service (QoS) constraints. First, we formulate the problem as a Mixed Integer Linear Program (MILP) that minimizes the total power consumption. We then formulate it as a Markov Decision Process (MDP) and propose a low complexity reinforcement-learning solution based on Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) to make user association decisions under the same constraints. Extensive multi-scenario simulations show that the proposed DNN-based policy achieves almost 10 times lower power consumption compared to the State-of-the-Art (SoA), while incurring significantly lower computational complexity than the optimal MILP, in a multi-node network with more than 140 base stations.

Index Terms—Terrestrial, Aerial, Space, TN-NTN, DNN, High-Altitude Platform Station (HAPS), Low Earth Orbit (LEO), User Association.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth of traffic in recent years is straining the limits of current 5G architectures. Mobile-device density has increased over the past decade and is projected to reach 125 billion devices by 2030 [1]. Accommodating this, while meeting ever more demanding service requirements, will require sixth generation (6G) networks to deliver substantially higher energy efficiency. To that end, the architecture must evolve toward a heterogeneous fabric integrating Terrestrial and Non-Terrestrial Networks (TN-NTNs) to serve users across diverse environments, from remote rural areas to dense urban centers.

However, user association and resource allocation in such integrated networks become increasingly complex, as aerial and space Base Stations (BSs) typically require more spectral resources than their terrestrial counterparts to meet a given Quality of Service (QoS). Moreover, given the limited resources, even under such integrated scenarios, a User Equipment (UE) needs to be associated with BSs subject to capacity and power constraints, while satisfying its service requirements.

Although network densification is a primary lever for increasing system capacity, it entails substantial energy and

cost overheads, with the Access Network (AN) emerging as the dominant energy bottleneck in next-generation 6G architectures [2]. Consequently, energy-efficient densification is imperative to a) reduce operational expenditure and b) advance environmentally sustainable infrastructures via lower power consumption. These demands call for sophisticated resource-allocation frameworks that: i) accommodate emerging 6G technologies (e.g., THz bands) and their constraints, ii) deliver end-to-end performance under stringent latency and throughput requirements, and iii) optimize network-wide energy efficiency. In turn, the convergence of terrestrial, aerial, and space segments in 6G networks necessitates innovative and energy-aware user association mechanisms that maintain QoS and safeguard service continuity.

A. Related work and Contribution

Research on terrestrial, aerial, and space integration has intensified in recent years, as efficient user association is pivotal for 6G sustainability. In [3]–[10], the proposed user association solutions may suffice for the studied use cases, even though a subset of the TN-NTN network is only addressed. In [3], the problem concerns aerial UEs that need to be accommodated by a part of the TN and a single Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellite for Urban Air Mobility (UAM) services. Similarly, [4] targets the aerial segment (specifically High-Altitude Platform Station (HAPS)–TN connectivity) with the goal of maximizing spectral efficiency while mitigating interference across the vertical network. Pursuing the same objective, [5] proposes a cloud-enabled HAPS offloading scheme that serves both aerial and terrestrial users under transmit-power and fronthaul capacity constraints. For disaster scenarios, [6] tackles the association problem by deploying not only HAPS but also Uncrewed Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) as intermediaries between the HAPS and the TN. Maritime services are considered in [7], combining UAVs with LEO satellites to meet heterogeneous requirements (from high-end terminals to simple data buoys) while emphasizing energy and spectral efficiency. In [8], the authors employ a Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) to maximize data services in a Space-Air-Ground Integrated Network (SAGIN), accounting for the LEO trajectory and

power consumption. Likewise, [9] trains a Deep Neural Network (DNN) (unsupervised learning with ensembling) that converges to a policy for terrestrial, aerial, and Geostationary Earth Orbit (GEO) satellite user association under power constraints. However, its single satellite-HAPS-ground network architecture limits scalability to more complex multi-node deployments. Finally, in [10], the authors propose a heuristic algorithm to tackle the joint problem of user association, VNF placement and traffic routing, focusing on increasing the energy efficiency of the network, which comprises numerous terrestrial and satellite BSs. Nevertheless, all the aforementioned works cannot guarantee energy efficiency, as they consider only parts of the three-dimensional (3D) network, with fewer service types and a less dynamic environment that considerably simplifies the problem.

In this paper, we propose a unified framework encompassing multi-altitude BSs, including terrestrial, aerial, and space segments. The proposed approach tackles the critical problem of optimizing BS-UE association in a highly heterogeneous environment, while jointly minimizing network-wide energy consumption across the integrated three-dimensional (3D) topology. To that end, our contribution is threefold: i) we formulate an optimal Mixed Integer Linear Program (MILP) model to serve as a benchmark for the proposed algorithm, ii) we propose a low-complexity DNN that associates UEs with the AN according to their service requirements, minimizes total power consumption and satisfies capacity and delay constraints, and iii) we conduct a thorough comparative evaluation against both the MILP optimum and state-of-the-art (SoA) schemes, demonstrating up to almost 9.8 times higher energy-efficiency gains and verifying suitability for real-time user association in 6G networks due to its low computational complexity and runtime performance.

The structure of the paper is as follows: Section II presents the system model and formulates the problem. Section III describes the proposed neural network solution, while Section IV evaluates its performance relative to optimal benchmarks and the SoA. Finally, Section V concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

Fig. 1. System model of the integrated terrestrial, aerial, and satellite network.

We consider an integrated 3D TN-NTN, as depicted in Fig. 1, consisting of terrestrial, aerial and space nodes. In the terrestrial domain, a set of macro gNodeBs (gNBs) is considered, denoted by S_G , which is overlaid by a set of Small Cells (SCs), denoted by S_{SC} . In the aerial domain, a set of HAPS is considered, denoted by S_H . In the space domain, the satellite set is restricted to LEO satellites, S_{LEO} .

We exclude Medium Earth Orbit (MEO) and GEO systems because LEO constellations are the only viable candidates for direct device access, primarily due to path-loss and latency considerations. A set of UEs, denoted by \mathcal{U} , is also considered with Guaranteed Bit Rate (GBR) requirements equal to d_u for UE u .

Given that the main goal of the studied problem is to maximize total energy efficiency, for GBR services this is equivalent to minimizing the total power expenditure in the AN subject to the GBR constraints. As a result, we focus on the total power consumption, measured in Watts (W), and so the MILP can be written as

$$\min \sum_{i \in S_{union}} p_i, \quad \text{s.t. (4) - (6)}, \quad (1)$$

where p_i is the total power consumption of BS i (terrestrial, aerial, space) belonging to the set $S_{union} := S_G \cup S_{SC} \cup S_H \cup S_{LEO}$. For the power model of BS i , we rely on the well-established linear BS power model introduced in [11], in which both the variable RF output power p_{out_i} and the total BS power consumption scale linearly, per transceiver chain (TRX).

$$p_i = N_{TRX_i}(p_{0_i} + \Delta p_i \cdot p_{out_i}), \quad \forall i \in S_{union}, \quad (2)$$

where N_{TRX_i} is the total number of transceiver chains of BS i , and p_{0_i} represents the minimum non-zero output (load-independent) power per TRX chain of BS i ; Δp_i is the slope of load-dependent power consumption, which receives different values based on the antenna type used [11]; p_{out_i} is the transmitted power consumption of BS i per TRX chain, given by

$$p_{out_i} = \frac{p_{max_i}}{c_{i,max}} \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} (x_{(i,u)} c_{(i,u)}), \quad (3)$$

where p_{max_i} is the maximum transmit power of BS i (a uniform power allocation per Physical Resource Block (PRB) is assumed) and $c_{i,max}$ is the maximum number of PRBs of BS i . The parameter $x_{(i,u)}$ is a binary link vector of the AN link between BS i and UE u , which takes the value 1 when UE u is connected to BS i and 0 otherwise, that is

$$x_{(i,u)} \in \{0, 1\}, \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \quad \forall i \in S_{union}. \quad (4)$$

In addition, the parameter $c_{(i,u)}$ is the number of PRBs needed to satisfy the QoS of UE u when connected to BS i . The capacity constraint of BS i can be then expressed as

$$\sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} x_{(i,u)} c_{(i,u)} \leq c_{i,max}, \quad \forall i \in S_{union}. \quad (5)$$

Furthermore, each UE u may connect to a single BS only, which is expressed as

$$\sum_{i \in S_{union}} x_{(i,u)} = 1, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}. \quad (6)$$

Each UE u associated with BS i is allocated $c_{(i,u)}$ PRBs, which denotes the number of PRBs needed to meet its requested rate, given the current link state, and is calculated as

$$c_{(i,u)} = \lceil \frac{d_u}{BW_{PRB} S E_{(i,u)}} \rceil, \quad (7)$$

where $\lceil \cdot \rceil$ is the ceiling operator, BW_{PRB} denotes the bandwidth of a PRB, $SE_{(i,u)}$ is the maximum achievable spectrum efficiency with an effective signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio ($SINR_{(i,u)}$), given by [12], when UE u connects to BS i .

III. PROPOSED POWER EFFICIENT RL-BASED ALGORITHM

The algorithm used to train the DNN is Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO), which is used for environments with discrete or continuous action spaces. The algorithm alternates between sampling data through the features fed through the environment and optimizing a clipped surrogate objective function using stochastic gradient descent. PPO can be implemented through an actor/critic architecture, where the actor estimates a stochastic policy and the critic estimates the value of the policy. The objective function clips the policy values to improve training stability. Based on [13]

$$L^{CLIP}(\theta) = \mathbb{E}[\min(r_t(\theta)\hat{A}_t, \text{clip}(r_t(\theta), 1 - \epsilon, 1 + \epsilon)\hat{A}_t)], \quad (8)$$

in which θ are the parameters of the actor that are randomly initialized and tuned during training thus improving the policy. $\hat{\mathbb{E}}$ are the experiences over multiple episodes following the current policy, specifically S denotes the current observed state, based on which the actor determines the action A using the policy $\pi_\theta(a_t|s_t)$. The reward R is observed and the next observation S' , along with the action and the last observation, is stored as an experience $\mathbb{E} = (S, A, R, S')$.

The value $r_t(\theta)$ is the fraction $\frac{\pi_\theta(a_t|s_t)}{\pi_{\theta_{old}}(a_t|s_t)}$ that is multiplied by the advantage function estimator \hat{A}_t , which in this problem is the Generalized Advantage Estimator (GAE) [14]. GAE computes the advantage function D_t (discounted sum of temporal difference errors)

$$D_t = \sum_{k=t}^{t+N-1} (\gamma\lambda)^{k-t} \delta_k, \quad (9)$$

where t is a single step, γ is the discount factor, λ is the GAE factor, and δ_k is the temporal difference error. Finally, ϵ is the clip factor that clips the gradients to improve stability during training.

The DNN architecture that is selected to solve the aforementioned problem is shown in Fig. 2. The selected neuron count is shown to sufficiently capture the full space of observations and actions within the network. As for the DNN input, certain observations have been picked that proved sufficient to accomplish the energy efficiency goal, without bloating the input layer with unneeded information. In each user association decision step, the following features were selected as input for the developed network of 144 BSs:

- 144 binary flags to track which BS is currently active or not.
- 144 values of the needed PRBs for a certain UE to connect to a certain BS, normalized and bounded between 0 and 1.
- 144 values of the remaining PRBs on the selected BS, normalized between -1 and 0.

Fig. 2. Actor network layer visualization.

- 144 values of the power per PRB multiplied by Δp_i and N_{TRX_i} for each BS, based on its type (gNb, SC, HAPS, LEO), and normalized between 0 and 1.
- 4 idle power values for each type of BS, normalized between 0 and 1.

Feature normalization is used for training stability and uniform feature importance, as non-normalized values would have biased the proposed agent's decision-making. The only non-normalized values are the 144 binary flags, which do not require normalization due to their binary nature.

During training, three different activation functions are tested, ReLU, Swish and ELU [15]; ReLU provides stability but converges more slowly than the other two, while Swish is able to converge faster than ReLU creating non-stable rewards, effectively never reaching the potential of the network. Among them, ELU has the best results, as it converged quickly to the best rewards across different scenarios while keeping the learning stable enough to avoid dips during training. Finally, having a bottleneck architecture (lessening neurons in each layer) helps the DNN have a higher understanding of the problem at hand, as it needs to mix the results of earlier layer neurons with the later layer neurons. This architecture forces the DNN to have a more abstract understanding of the problem and its solutions.

Hard constraints are implemented to enable the DNN to reach its energy efficiency objective while preserving resource availability in each BS. During each training step, once a BS is selected, the step function verified whether this action would result in resource depletion. If the selected BS retains zero or more PRBs after the action, the step function proceeds normally to the reward function. Otherwise, a flag is triggered, and a standard penalty of -1 is returned as an experience alongside the state-action-next state tuple (S, A, S') .

The action space for each user association decision step consists of a set of all BS indices from which a UE has to select one BS for association. The Reward Function is structured so that the agent reaches the energy efficiency goal, minimizing the power consumption of the network, as follows

$$R_s = 1 - \frac{\Delta P_s - P_{i_{min}}}{P_{i_{max}} - P_{i_{min}}}, \quad R_s \in [0, 1], \quad (10)$$

where R_s is the step reward, ΔP_s is the power increase of the step, $P_{i_{min}}$ and $P_{i_{max}}$ are the minimum and maximum power consumption values, respectively. Furthermore, R_s is bounded between 0 and 1, so that the rewards are also normalized.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In the current section, the employed evaluation scenario as well as the simulation results of the proposed framework compared to optimal benchmarks and SoA are presented.

A. Evaluation scenario

Table I summarizes the simulation parameters for the heterogeneous AN. The network comprises four parts: a macro gNB, SCs, HAPS, and LEO satellites. Specifically, the terrestrial domain includes one gNB overlaid with eight SCs (two clusters of four), the aerial domain comprises one HAPS, and the space domain consists of 134 LEOs. The satellite orbits correspond to deployed/existing constellations, including satellites from Iridium, Eutelsat OneWeb and Starlink. Satellite positions are computed based on Two-Line Element (TLE) data obtained from [16]. Without loss of generality, the simulation area is centred on the city centre of Thessaloniki, Greece. For each scenario, 40 UEs with random spatial distribution within the gNB coverage area are considered, each with varying service requirements in terms of delay and rate. P_t denotes the transmission power in dBm, L_{Tx} and G_{Tx} are the transmitter losses in dB and antenna gain in dBi, respectively. N_F is the noise figure of the receivers measured in dB and G/T is the antenna gain-to-noise-temperature ratio, which is measured in dB/K.

TABLE I
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Part of the network	gNB	SC	HAPS	LEO
N	1	8	1	134
f (GHz)	2	2	28	28
BW (GHz)	0.02	0.02	0.2	0.4
N_{TRX_i}	128	32	64	128
P_{0_i} (W)	145	6.8	1	1
Δp_i	4.2	4	2	1
P_t (dBm)	46	38	40	60
L_{Tx} (dB)	1	1	1	1
G_{Tx} (dBi)	23	20	32	36
N_F (dB)	7	7	7	7
G/T (dB/K)	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5
Type of service	Rate (Mbps)	Latency (ms)	Duration (sec)	Share (%)
Web	[0.6-1]	500	20	20
VoIP	[0.384-0.64]	100	100	20
Streaming	[5-24]	100	360	39
Gaming	[0.24-0.5]	60	300	6
Ultra RT AI/ML	[15-25]	1	40	15

B. Training process

The training and simulation results for the proposed Reinforcement Learning (RL) algorithm and the heuristics are created in MATLAB R2024b, leveraging its RL Toolbox, while the optimal solution it is developed and executed in IBM CPLEX. For the DNN's convergence, the technique of curriculum learning is employed, which uses a three-phase training.

TABLE II
HYPERPARAMETER VALUES USED IN ALL TRAINING PHASES

Hyperparameter	Value
Discount Factor (γ)	0.99
Experience Horizon	250
Batch Size	65
Entropy Loss Weight	0.01
Actor Learn Rate	10^{-5}
Critic Learn Rate	2×10^{-5}
GAE Factor	0.95
Clip Factor (ϵ)	0.2

Phase I (foundations): train on simplified, homogeneous scenarios so the model internalizes the basic principles of user association. Phase II (service diversity): introduce heterogeneous UEs and service classes (latency/throughput targets) so the model learns that different demand profiles require different association patterns. Phase III (full variability): expose the DNN to a wide range of network states, i.e., varying loads, mobility, channel conditions, and BS availability, to promote generalization. This progressive curriculum improves sample efficiency, stabilizes training, and accelerates convergence.

Table II shows the hyperparameter values that are used during the multi-phase training. These values are selected via iterative tuning (coarse-to-fine sweeps and ablations) and adjusted per phase to stabilize training and improve generalization. The discount factor γ is a scalar value between 0 and 1 that determines how much the actor will prioritize future rewards, with values near 0 prioritizing present rewards, while values near 1 prioritizing future rewards. The experience horizon is the maximum number of time steps that an agent can collect experience during a single episode, while the batch size is a random set of 65 experiences drawn from the total of 250 that will be used to update the agent's policy. Entropy loss weight, which is specified as a scalar value between 0 and 1, is a parameter that promotes agent exploration by applying a penalty for being too certain about which action to take, that can help the agent escape local optima. Learning rates determine how much the actor and critic networks' parameters are adjusted based on the computed gradients; higher rates tend to converge faster but may provide suboptimal results. GAE factor controls the bias-variance trade-off in advantage by smoothing estimates across different time horizons. A value of 0.95 heavily weighs longer-term information while incorporating shorter-term corrections, creating more stable learning signals than using immediate or fully discounted rewards alone. The clip factor ϵ in PPO limits the extent to which the policy can change during a single update, preventing large policy changes that could destabilize training.

During Phase I training (Fig. 3), the model runs 4000 episodes on a fixed scenario comprising 144 BSs overall. The rewards exhibit a modest upward trend, with convergence apparent after ~ 3500 episodes. However, due to the limited diversity in the dataset, i.e., each one of the 4000 episodes is identical (all BSs and UEs maintained fixed positions and service demands), the learning process is inherently constrained, preventing faster or more robust generalization. This initial

training step is intentionally designed to allow the agent to become familiar with the user association dynamics of the network before introducing variability.

Fig. 3. First DNN training over 4000 same iteration scenarios.

During Phase II training (Fig. 4), we maintain the same BS topology; however, the UEs vary in both position and service requirements across 10 distinct scenarios. This variation enables the agent to adapt to different service patterns and solutions. To ensure a more effective training, each scenario is replicated 1000 times and randomly shuffled to prevent the agent from overfitting and promote convergence to a more generalized policy. Compared to Phase I, the rewards exhibit a significant improvement, following an almost linear upward trend originating from a significant reduction in power consumption across episodes in this phase.

In the third and final training (Phase III) (Fig. 5), we maintain the same network architecture and BS configuration, but the topology is now updated for each scenario. The UEs are assigned varying locations and service requirements across 9900 distinct episodes. These scenarios are then triplicated and randomly reordered to ensure a more uniform distribution of learning experience. The purpose of this training approach is to enable the agent to preserve the strong performance achieved in the initial 10 scenarios while developing a broadly generalized policy capable of handling 9900 diverse scenarios.

C. Simulation results

The effectiveness of the proposed agent is evaluated through 100 independent scenarios of randomized BS/UE locations and service requirements as detailed in [11]. It attains a mean reward of 39.6267 with a standard deviation of only ± 1.1467 . The proposed algorithm is compared against an optimal solution and two SoA approaches: i) the Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP)-based approach [17], which leverages the default user association criterion that associates

Fig. 4. Second DNN training on 10 varied scenarios with different UE services and topologies, expanded $\times 1000$ and shuffled to prevent overfitting.

Fig. 5. Third DNN training on 9900 scenarios with varied UE services and topologies, tripled and shuffled.

the UE based on the highest received signal strength, and ii) the TERA algorithm [10], a heuristic approach that associates UEs by minimizing incremental power consumption in the network.

Across the 100 scenarios, the proposed model achieved a mean power consumption of 162.77 W, substantially lower than the RSRP-based method (1.6 kW). The TERA algorithm performed better than the RSRP-based approach but consumed more power than the proposed model, with a mean of 190.31 W. The optimal solution achieved the lowest mean power consumption at 19.53 W, as shown in Fig. 6. Consequently, the proposed solution is 9.8 times and 14.5% more energy-efficient

Fig. 6. Power consumption comparison among Optimal, RL-Proposed, TERA and RSRP-based algorithms.

Fig. 7. Comparison of time execution among Optimal, RL-Proposed, TERA and RSRP-based algorithms.

than the RSRP-based approach and the TERA algorithm, respectively, and is the closest to the optimal solution among practical schemes.

The primary trade-off among all evaluated solutions lies in their computational complexity, as illustrated in Fig. 7. The proposed algorithm achieves a balanced compromise between energy/power efficiency and complexity, achieving real-time suitability with a mean execution time of 19.4 ms per scenario (~ 2780 times faster in average than the optimal solution, which, with a mean of 54 s, is impractical for real-time use). The least complex method is the RSRP-based algorithm, which achieves the lowest mean execution time of 9.3 ms but performs poorly in terms of power consumption, making it unsuitable for energy-efficient operation. As for the TERA algorithm, it represents the second-best alternative, exhibiting power consumption similar to the proposed approach but requires 12.9 times higher mean execution time (250 ms, compared to 19.4 ms for the proposed approach).

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we present a RL-based approach for energy-efficient user association in integrated terrestrial and non-terrestrial 6G networks. By developing a DNN trained with PPO, we tackle the complex challenge of maximizing energy efficiency of a heterogeneous network comprising terrestrial BSs, HAPs, and LEO satellites. Our approach demonstrates significant enhancements over current SoA methods, achieving significant improvements in energy efficiency while meeting user service requirements. The three-phase curriculum learning

strategy proved essential for the DNN to effectively learn the intricate relationships between PRB allocation and power consumption, ultimately reducing average power consumption by up to 9.8 times compared to the SoA approaches, while achieving ~ 2780 times faster runtime than the optimal solution. These results establish the proposed algorithm's suitability for real-time deployment in sustainable 3D 6G networks. Future work will extend the proposed framework to jointly allocate communication, computational and storage resources, and will further improve the algorithm's performance.

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